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**Data-based surrogate modeling for simulation of blood
flow in vessel-like model**

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Abstract

While CFD simulations constantly become more complex, data availability also increases. By exploiting this abundance, modal decomposition and model reduction techniques exhibit an immense potential to improve hemodynamic research. On this behalf, this work derives the *dynamic mode decomposition* (DMD) method and examines its capabilities based on a straight vessel-like geometry. Furthermore, as patient-specific treatment demands fast adaptation and investigation of flow parameters, a Navier Stokes equation-based modeling approach is introduced regarding the vessel's mass-inflow as a system variable. While calculations show that the basic DMD algorithm provides quantitatively accurate results, the applied method of the *dynamic mode decomposition with control* (DMDc) lacks functional outcomes. Furthermore, different characteristics and variants of the method are demonstrated, providing a basis for various future assessments and applications.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Model order reduction

Our world is driven by constant growth and fast technological development. In terms of, e.g., patient-specific medical treatment, higher power efficiency, autonomous driving, or metabolism modeling it exists a general need for increased accuracy concerning calculations and mathematical models describing real-world problems. Thus, these models become constantly more complex, demanding high computational resources, i.e., time and memory. Although memory is comparably cheap those days and computing power is exponentially growing [19, 22], calculation time is still a critical point. Consequently, it is reasonable to research the reduction of computational costs in a mathematical sense to ensure later appropriate usage in, e.g., real-time applications, simulation, control, or optimization.

Modeling dynamical systems leads to nonlinear ordinary differential equations (ODE), partial differential equations (PDE), or even coupled systems of those. In terms of the more complex ones, methods to obtain explicit solutions usually do not yet exist. So, numerical methods like the finite differences or finite volume method (FVM) are applied. These approaches split the system into a set of smaller, discretized subsystems. Consequently, the solutions are generally large-scale. It is thus plausible that their information content lives on a significantly smaller subspace. Therefore, reducing the underlying and governing information is of great interest to engineers and scientists. This field of research is called *model order reduction* (MOR). One popular approach approximates those large-scale systems with their most essential modes. For instance, the fundamental solution of a basic linear dynamical system consisting of the exponential function justifies keeping or estimating the slow eigenvectors since the effect of the fast vanishes quickly in time. The smaller systems obtained by MOR approaches are called *reduced-order models* (ROM). Besides having the advantage of being less computationally demanding than the original large-scale version, ROMs approximate the actual behavior generally well.

1.2. Data-driven MOR and equation-free methods

Rising possibilities in numerical research and experiments lead to an increasing amount of data collected and analyzed worldwide.

Today, data is abundant. Moreover, it is well known that this data contains a rich amount of information characterizing the governing behavior of its source. This property is of great relevance due to the amount of readily available data and the fact that closed modeling becomes disproportionately expensive or even impossible at a certain point.

This so-called *fourth paradigm of scientific discovery* [7] spawns a significant number of mathematical techniques and machine learning approaches to characterize patterns in extensive data or to describe the underlying behavior in a low-dimensional form. This approach is called *data-driven model order reduction*. (DDMOR)

The curious reader might also encounter the term *equation-free* in literature in this context. It simply describes that a „methodology bypasses the derivation of macroscopic evolution equations when these equations conceptually exist but are not available in closed form“. [11] Hence, one characterizes a behavior without using concrete equations but, e.g., by snapshot data.

1.3. Modal Decomposition vs. System Identification

There are mainly two established applications in DDMOR: modal decomposition and system identification.

The community of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) considerably drove the first one. [12] Whereas the underlying governing equations like the Navier-Stokes equations are usually infinite-dimensional PDEs and thus highly computationally demanding, fluid dynamics often exhibit low-dimensional behavior. [29] It is consequently of high interest to „extract coherent structures in the form of temporal and spatial modes.“[31] For example, already three ODEs can describe the main characteristics of a laminar flow past a two-dimensional cylinder. [20] This approach is representative that the system’s dimension is significantly smaller than the number of measurements. [21] Examples of modal decomposition methods are *proper orthogonal decomposition* (POD), *balanced proper orthogonal decomposition* (BPOD), and *dynamic mode decomposition* (DMD). The last is investigated in this work.

In contrast, system identification methods aim to produce linear input-output models, usually using the system’s frequency- or time-domain data. [12] This type of data is mostly utilized in terms of control or simulation. In this case, the system’s rank is typically higher than the number of observables. [21] Representatives of this methodology are the *eigensystem realization algorithm* (ERA) and the *observer Kalman filter identification* (OKID). [8, 9, 10] It was discovered that both exhibit a connection to DMD. [12, 21, 29]

2. Methodology

2.1. Dynamic mode decomposition

Dynamic mode decomposition is a data-driven, thus equation-free, methodology to characterize a system's dominant, underlying dynamics. It can accurately describe a complex dynamical system by decomposing it into its dominant „spatiotemporal coherent structures.“ These insights then deliver the groundwork for further diagnostics of the system characteristics, future-state prediction, or even control. [12]

DMD is the construction of a best-fit linear dynamic of given snapshot data in a least-squares sense. Surprisingly, the linear dynamics obtained by DMD also work very well for data of nonlinear systems. [12] This property gets „theoretical justification within the spectral theory of the Koopman operator.“ [18] However, the idea itself is not based on the linearization of the nonlinear system. [23] The DMD procedure can be understood as the decomposition of a „finite-dimensional linear model that approximates the infinite-dimensional Koopman operator.“ [12] Note that a general explanation and derivation of the Koopman theory will be no part of this work.

For means of relevance and motivation, the following mathematical introduction to DMD adapted from [12, 21, 27, 29] will thus be explained based on a linear dynamical system $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathcal{A} \cdot \mathbf{x}$. The analytic solution for this system is given as

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \exp(\mathcal{A}t) \cdot \mathbf{x}_1 \quad (2.1.1)$$

with \mathbf{x}_1 representing the initial value at time $t_1 = 0$. If the eigendecomposition of \mathcal{A} exists with $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{V}\mathfrak{A}\mathcal{V}^{-1}$, it is possible to rewrite the expression (2.1.1) using the definition of the matrix exponential:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathcal{V} \exp(\mathfrak{A}t) \mathcal{V}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{x}_1 = \mathcal{V} \exp(\mathfrak{A}t) \mathbf{d} \quad (2.1.2)$$

where \mathbf{d} are the coordinates of \mathbf{x}_1 in the eigenvector-space \mathcal{V} .

$$\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathcal{V} \cdot \mathbf{d} \quad (2.1.3)$$

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathcal{V}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_1 \quad (2.1.4)$$

Furthermore, discretizing (2.1.1) in time delivers:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \exp(\mathcal{A} \cdot h) \cdot \mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x}_k \quad (2.1.5)$$

with h being the time step size of the used snapshots. We see that both \mathcal{A} and \mathbf{A} have the same eigenvectors, whereas the eigenvalues are scaled by

$$\mu_i = \frac{\ln(\lambda_i)}{h} \quad (2.1.6)$$

with μ_i being the eigenvalues in \mathfrak{A} and λ_i being the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} , i.e. $\Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots)$. This relation, in combination with (2.1.2) and (2.1.4), further delivers the following relation for the states

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathcal{V} \Lambda^{k-1} \cdot \mathbf{d} \quad (2.1.7)$$

Assume we have some state snapshots $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $k = 1 \dots m$ and $n \gg 1$. Arranging them in two shifted matrices, we get

$$\mathbb{X} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & \dots & | \\ \mathbf{x}_1 & \mathbf{x}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{x}_{m-1} \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.1.8)$$

$$\mathbb{X}' = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \mathbf{x}_2 & \mathbf{x}_3 & \dots & \mathbf{x}_m \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.1.9)$$

for which the expression (2.1.5) holds with

$$\mathbb{X}' = \mathbf{A} \mathbb{X} \quad (2.1.10)$$

So the aim is to find an $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ that best fits this linear expression for the collected snapshots. That can be obtained by minimizing the linear regression error $\forall \mathbf{x}_k$ in \mathbb{X} , i.e.

$$\min_A \|\mathbb{X}' - \mathbf{A} \mathbb{X}\|_F \quad (2.1.11)$$

Since \mathbb{X} is usually not regular, it is possible to solve the inner expression using the pseudo inverse

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbb{X}' \mathbb{X}^\dagger \quad (2.1.12)$$

with the pseudo inverse given as $\mathbb{X}^\dagger = (\mathbb{X}^T \mathbb{X})^{-1} \cdot \mathbb{X}^T$. Assume the SVD of \mathbb{X}

$$\mathbb{X} \stackrel{\text{SVD}}{=} \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^* \approx \hat{\mathbf{U}} \hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}} \hat{\mathbf{V}}^* \quad (2.1.13)$$

with $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m-1}$ and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times m-1}$ from the economic SVD and $\hat{\mathbf{U}} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times r}$, $\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, $\hat{\mathbf{V}} \in \mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times r}$ with the truncation value $r < m - 1$. Note that the left- and right-singular-vector matrices are unitary or semi-unitary, respectively. Now we can effectively replace this pseudo inverse expression with

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{X}^\dagger &= (\mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^T\mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^*)^{-1}\mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{U}^* \\
&= (\mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^2\mathbf{V}^*)^{-1}\mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{U}^* \\
&= \mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-2}\mathbf{V}^*\mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{U}^* \\
&= \mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{U}^* \\
&\approx \hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{U}}^*
\end{aligned} \tag{2.1.14}$$

Using this result, we can rewrite (2.1.12) to

$$\mathbf{A} \approx \mathbb{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{U}}^* \tag{2.1.15}$$

which represents the best rank r approximation for \mathbf{A} . [5]

Nevertheless, this \mathbf{A} still depends on n . So, since \mathbf{A} lies in the image of \mathbb{X}' , it has at most rank $m - 1$. For means of computational efficiency, we thus project it on a lower subspace using a Galerkin-Projection with $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ from the SVD in (2.1.13). Assume the projection $\mathbf{x} \approx \hat{\mathbf{U}} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}$. In terms of Galerkin, that means

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbf{A} \hat{\mathbf{U}} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k \tag{2.1.16}$$

Hence we get the low-rank projection of \mathbf{A} :

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbf{A} \hat{\mathbf{U}} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbb{X}' \hat{\mathbf{V}} \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}^{-1} \tag{2.1.17}$$

The DMD procedure aims to characterize the system without knowing closed-form underlying equations. Regarding (2.1.7), it is thus appropriate to compute the eigendecomposition of \mathbf{A} or $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, respectively.

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \tag{2.1.18}$$

Interestingly, the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} are already given by $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}$. Its eigenvectors $\boldsymbol{\nu}$, however, i.e., the *exact DMD modes*, need to be reconstructed by:

$$\boldsymbol{\nu} = \mathbb{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}^{-1}\mathbf{W} \tag{2.1.19}$$

Apart from that, there exists another expression for the eigenvectors with

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\nu}} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}\mathbf{W} \tag{2.1.20}$$

which was introduced in [24]. The latter are called the *projected DMD modes*. This naming is because $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\nu}}$ is the projection of $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ onto the range of \mathbb{X} . This and the proof of $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}$ can be found in [29].

Application

As discussed earlier, the so-far obtained results can be used for different aims.

First, the DMD model can be used for control. In this case, usually, the ROM is used.

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k \quad (2.1.21)$$

Using this version, the modes do not need to be computed. The obtained states are of rank r . If the states need to be mapped onto the original space n , a projection $\mathbf{x} = \hat{\mathbf{U}} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ is applied with $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ from (2.1.13).

A second important application is the diagnostic and investigation of the fundamental characteristics of the system's behavior. Therefore, the columns of the exact and projected DMD modes \mathbf{V} and $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$, respectively, contain the most relevant information.

Third, there is future-state prediction and reconstruction. Three possible approaches exist: the discrete ROM, the discrete modal projection, and the time-domain solution.

The discrete modal projection is based on the DMD modes and is given by equation (2.1.7). A numerically stable calculation of \mathbf{d} will be explained in more detail in section 2.3.

The time-domain solution is given in (2.1.2). This equation can be used to calculate the states at any time t , which still match the solutions of the discretized versions. The connection can be derived using equations (2.1.6) and (2.1.7):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_k &= \mathbf{V} \Lambda^{k-1} \cdot \mathbf{d} \\ &\stackrel{(2.1.6)}{=} \mathbf{V} \left(\exp(\mathcal{A} \cdot h) \right)^{k-1} \cdot \mathbf{d} \\ &= \mathbf{V} \exp(\mathcal{A} \cdot (k-1)h) \cdot \mathbf{d} \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.22)$$

Thus, at times $t = (k-1) \cdot h$, the time-domain solution produces equivalent solutions as the discrete models.

No projection onto the high dimensional space is necessary in the latter cases since \mathbf{V} already depends on n . Furthermore, the ROM matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ does not have to be stored for later use. It is to be noted that the discretized states \mathbf{x}_k highly depend on the modes \mathbf{V} . Using the exact DMD modes in (2.1.19), expression (2.1.3) delivers the snapshot $\mathbf{x}_{1,rec} = \mathbf{x}_2$. That is because the exact DMD modes live in the image of \mathbb{X}' . The projected DMD modes in (2.1.20), however, provide the snapshot $\mathbf{x}_{1,rec} = \mathbf{x}_1$ at index 1.

Similar to (2.1.22), the connection between the modal projection and the ROM can be shown.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{x}_{k+1} &\stackrel{(2.1.7)(2.1.19)}{=} \mathbf{V}\Lambda^{k-1} \cdot \mathbf{d} \\
&\stackrel{(2.1.19)(2.3.8)}{=} \mathbb{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{W}\Lambda^{k-1}(\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{W})^{-1}\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{x}_1 \\
&\stackrel{(2.1.15)(2.1.18)}{\approx} \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{U}}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{k-1} \underbrace{\mathbf{W}(\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{W})^{-1}\mathbf{W}^*}_{\approx \mathbb{I}} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_1 \\
&\stackrel{(2.1.16)}{\approx} \hat{\mathbf{U}}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_1
\end{aligned} \tag{2.1.23}$$

Because different approximations are used, the results of both methods are likely to vary slightly.

2.2. Dynamic Mode Decomposition with control

This section will introduce *dynamic mode decomposition with control* (DMDc) using [21]. In practice, it is often desired to examine a dynamic system's underlying characteristics that are affected by external influences. In some fields, it is even of interest to describe and understand how the impact of these influences occurs. This algorithmic approach is based on the classical DMD with the difference that measurements of the states \mathbf{x}_k and the control inputs $\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^p$ are used. In addition to the capabilities mentioned above, it also delivers an input-output ROM, which is helpful in prediction and often crucial in the design of controllers.

Assume having a dynamic system with no given closed-form equations and with unknown inherent control or input, respectively. In terms of states and inputs, we model their relationship in the following discrete linear form

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} \approx \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{u}_k \tag{2.2.1}$$

Here, \mathbf{B} describes the influence of the input onto the system, whereas \mathbf{A} characterizes the underlying, unperturbed system. Based on this, we can define every discrete time step by

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{A}^{k-1}\mathbf{x}_1 + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \mathbf{A}^{k-1-i} \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(i) \tag{2.2.2}$$

Arranging the state snapshots again like in (2.1.8) and equally setting the inputs $\mathbf{u}_1 \dots \mathbf{u}_{m-1}$ in the matrix $\mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m-1}$, we can rewrite (2.2.1) in the following closed linear matrix equation.

$$\mathbb{X}' \approx \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathcal{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{X} \\ \mathcal{Y} \end{bmatrix} \tag{2.2.3}$$

As this gives us now a familiar DMD form like in (2.1.10), we can likewise apply the DMD relation for the desired matrix \mathbf{G}

$$\mathbf{G} = \mathbb{X}' \cdot \mathcal{K}^\dagger \quad (2.2.4)$$

This includes the necessary Frobenius-norm and accordingly, the SVD applied on the big measurement and control snapshot matrix \mathcal{K} :

$$\min_G \|\mathbb{X}' - \mathbf{G}\mathcal{K}\|_F \quad (2.2.5)$$

$$\mathcal{K} \stackrel{\text{SVD}}{=} \mathbf{U}_o \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o \mathbf{V}_o^* \approx \hat{\mathbf{U}}_o \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_o \hat{\mathbf{V}}_o^* \quad (2.2.6)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_o \in \mathbb{C}^{n+p \times n+p}$, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o \in \mathbb{R}^{n+p \times m-1}$ and $\mathbf{V}_o \in \mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times m-1}$ as well as $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_o \in \mathbb{C}^{n+p \times s}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_o \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$, $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_o \in \mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times s}$ with the truncation value $s < m - 1$. As the matrix \mathcal{K} is necessarily larger than the previous \mathbf{A} , the DMDc truncation value s is larger than the r from classic DMD.

Considering (2.1.15), it is suitable to separate the left-singular-vector matrix $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_o$ into two parts to find approximations of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B}

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G} &\approx \bar{\mathbf{G}} = \mathbb{X}' \cdot \mathbf{V}_o \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_o^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_o^* \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{X}' \mathbf{V}_o \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_o^{-1} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{o,1}^* & \mathbb{X}' \mathbf{V}_o \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_o^{-1} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{o,2}^* \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.7)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{o,1} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times s}$, and $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{o,2} \in \mathbb{C}^{p \times s}$ respectively. Nevertheless, this is still computationally inappropriate since both \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} still depend on $n \gg 1$. Thus, we aim for an approximation of rank $s < n$ holding

$$\mathbf{x} \approx \mathbf{P} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^s, \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n \quad (2.2.8)$$

This POD approach can be derived again using an SVD. However, unlike DMD, it would be wrong to use $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_o$ for the projection onto the relevant subspace for the state's evolution. That is because $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_o$ is determining the input space of \mathbf{G} , which now includes the states \mathbf{x}_k and the inputs \mathbf{u}_k . From (2.2.7), we know that we need to extract the output space of \mathbb{X}' to perform the desired POD projection like in (2.2.8). [12, 21] Thus, we get

$$\mathbb{X}' \stackrel{\text{SVD}}{=} \mathbf{U}_x \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_x \mathbf{V}_x^* \approx \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_x \hat{\mathbf{V}}_x^* \quad (2.2.9)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_x \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times s}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_x \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$, and $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_x \in \mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times s}$. Consequently, we can define the lower subspace projection similar to (2.1.16).

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{A}} &= \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x^* \mathbf{A} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x^* \cdot \mathbb{X}' \hat{\mathbf{V}}_o \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_o^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{o,1}^* \cdot \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x \\ \tilde{\mathbf{B}} &= \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x^* \mathbf{B} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x^* \cdot \mathbb{X}' \hat{\mathbf{V}}_o \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_o^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{o,2}^* \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.10)$$

These two projected matrices reveal a low-rank approximation of (2.2.1) with

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_k \quad (2.2.11)$$

As for DMD, it is a goal in DMDc to determine the relevant underlying dynamics of the system in a reduced form. So we compute the eigendecomposition $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{\Lambda}$. Lastly, we can state the reconstruction of the original dynamic modes in an equivalent manner like in DMD:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbb{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}_o\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}}_o^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{o,1}^*\hat{\mathbf{U}}_x \cdot \mathbf{W} \quad (2.2.12)$$

Application

This approach can easily be adapted to parametric systems in a broader context. We do not consider \mathbf{u}_k to represent the discretized control input snapshots for this aim. It is then a constant scalar or vector representing the parameters of interest. In this way, it becomes possible to quickly provide insides into the influence of the parameters on the system. Therefore it would not be necessary always to recompute the whole system with the new values.

As opposed to the basic DMD version, the underlying dynamics of the system with inherent perturbation have no algebraic time-domain solution. The absence is due to the convolution sum in (2.2.2) or the corresponding differential equation's convolution integral. Consequently, the resulting modal projection also does not exist for DMDc. Thus, the DMDc modes in (2.2.12) can mainly be used to characterize the dynamics of the underlying, unperturbed system. This is because \mathbf{v} is based on $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$.

Like in DMD, states \mathbf{x}_k can be computed using the ROM in (2.2.1). The projection onto the original space of dimension n is made by $\mathbf{x} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_x \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}$.

2.3. Dynamic mode decomposition for large data

In the following, I will present a more memory-efficient vector-space approach which was first introduced in [28] and later modified in [1]. In computational fluid dynamics and other research fields using large coupled systems requiring high accuracy, the addressed snapshots might rapidly grow in their size. At a certain point, this can lead to numerical instabilities and high computational costs when the snapshot matrices have to be loaded into the memory. It is thus of great advantage to adapt the general working procedure of DMD into a more computationally beneficial form.

In terms of a preliminary consideration, contemplate the DMD modes $\boldsymbol{\nu}_k$ and eigenvalues λ_k obtained in (2.1.18) and (2.1.19). From (2.1.7), it may be seen that they can be scaled such that

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \lambda_i^{k-1} \phi_k \quad (2.3.1)$$

with ϕ_k being the *scaled DMD modes*. This equation results from the spectral analysis of nonlinear flows in terms of the Koopman operator. [23] In combination with (2.1.3), one then obtains the scaling relation

$$\phi_k = \nu_k \cdot d_k \quad (2.3.2)$$

To begin with, consider the SVD in (2.1.13). In the case of huge data, it would be inefficient or even impossible to load the full \mathbb{X} matrix into memory. To avoid that, we use the *method of snapshots* [26] with a correlation matrix $\mathbf{H} = \mathbb{X}^* \cdot \mathbb{X}$. Its elements are given by the inner product

$$(\mathbb{X}^* \cdot \mathbb{X})_{j,k} = \langle \mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{x}_k \rangle \quad j, k = 1 \dots m - 1 \quad (2.3.3)$$

which can simply be computed as $(\mathbf{H})_{j,k} = \mathbf{x}_j^* \mathbf{x}_k$ in the case of an L_2 space. Note that it's possible to calculate those elements one after the other if necessary while having only two snapshots in memory at any time. Moreover, since \mathbf{H} is symmetric, computational resources can be saved.

The SVD can thus be replaced by computing the eigendecomposition of \mathbf{H} . This approach is numerically more efficient since the operation is applied to an $(m - 1) \times (m - 1)$ instead of an SVD on an $n \times (m - 1)$ matrix. We get

$$\mathbf{H}\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}\Theta \quad (2.3.4)$$

Similar to an SVD, the eigenvalues, and their eigenvectors have to be sorted in descending order. Note that the columns of \mathbf{V} are the right-singular vectors from (2.1.13) and $\Theta = \Sigma^2$. Furthermore, it is thus possible to reconstruct the left-singular vectors \mathbf{U} from

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{X}^*\mathbb{X} &= \mathbf{V}\Sigma^2\mathbf{V}^* \\ \mathbb{X}^*\mathbb{X}\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1} &= \mathbf{V}\Sigma \\ \mathbf{U} &= \mathbb{X}\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1} = \mathbb{X}\mathbf{V}\Theta^{-\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.5)$$

The next DMD step is to project the obtained representation of \mathbf{A} in (2.1.15) onto a lower subspace in (2.1.17). That again includes a full snapshot matrix. By using the reconstructed \mathbf{U} , we can relax the computation of $\mathbf{U}^*\mathbb{X}'$ in terms of memory usage. For that, consider $\mathbf{H}' = \mathbf{H}_{1:m-1,2:m-1}$ and the column vector $(\mathbf{H}'')_i = \langle x_m, x_i \rangle$ for $i = 1 \dots m - 1$. We get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}^*\mathbb{X}' &= \Theta^{-\frac{1}{2}}\mathbf{V}^*\mathbb{X}^*\mathbb{X}' \\ &= \Theta^{-\frac{1}{2}}\mathbf{V}^*[\mathbf{H}'\mathbf{H}''] \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.6)$$

With this result, (2.1.17) can be transformed into a new formula for $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{\Theta}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{V}^* [\mathbf{H}' \mathbf{H}'''] \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Theta}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.3.7)$$

Since we can reuse a part of the already computed correlation matrix, we reduce the number of necessary inner products at this point from $(m-1) \times (m-1)$ to $(m-1)$. We can now again compute the eigendecomposition of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ like in (2.1.18). The unscaled DMD modes can then be computed either using (2.1.19) or (2.1.20), respectively. To obtain the scaled modes in (2.3.2), we still must compute \mathbf{d} or $d_k \forall k = 1 \dots m-1$, respectively. We get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d} &\stackrel{(2.1.4)}{=} \mathbf{V}^\dagger \mathbf{x}_1 \\ &= (\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{V})^{-1} \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{x}_1 \\ &\stackrel{(2.1.20)}{=} (\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{W})^{-1} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{U}^* \mathbf{x}_1 \\ &\stackrel{(2.3.5)}{=} (\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{W})^{-1} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{\Theta}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{V}^* \mathbb{X}^* \mathbf{x}_1 \\ &= (\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{W})^{-1} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{\Theta}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{H}_{*,1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.8)$$

Adding this result to (2.3.2) using again (2.1.20) for ν_k and (2.3.5), we finally obtain the scaled DMD modes

$$\Phi = \left(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{W} \right) \mathbf{D} = \mathbb{X} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Theta}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{D} \quad (2.3.9)$$

Without using the big snapshot matrix, we can state every scaled DMD mode ϕ_k as

$$\phi_k = \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \mathbf{x}_i(\mathbf{T})_{i,k} \quad (2.3.10)$$

with $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Theta}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{D}$ and $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{d})$ to include the desired scaling with d_k in every column of \mathbf{T} .

Application

The possible applications of the presented algorithmic results correspond to those of classic DMD. Only the approaches for future-state prediction and reconstruction need to be discussed separately. The ROM variant is similar to (2.1.21). Again, \mathbf{d} and Φ are not necessary to be computed. With the given procedure, however, it is not possible to project the obtained states memory efficiently back onto the original dimension.

The modal projection and the time-domain solution do not differ from the original version. Here, the DMD modes \mathbf{V} are obtained using equation (2.3.10), when the matrix \mathbf{D} in \mathbf{T} is omitted.

Future-state prediction and reconstruction can also be carried out by equation (2.3.1). Mind that this is just another expression for the modal projection in (2.1.7).

3. Modeling and Problem Description

For instance, in cerebral aneurysm therapy, CFD-based investigations have immense potential. This numerical analysis makes it possible to speed up device design optimization, reduce animal studies, enable patient-specific treatment, or improve approval procedures. However, it still cannot live up to its full potential due to the remaining requirements of assumptions and simplifications. Moreover, without a consistent and accurate pre- and post-simulation, this powerful methodology cannot yet provide reliable information. Hence, patient-specific CFD blood simulation is only as precise as its input data and simulation setup. Ideally, the information on desired hemodynamic parameters like velocity, pressure, or even spatial wall characteristics could be at one's disposal at any point in time and space. Nonetheless, this is not always the case. A review [3] of several independent studies highlights that it is crucial to carefully select a simulation setup appropriate to the intended research question. This involves, e.g., inlet and outlet boundary conditions, time-step sizes, spatial resolution and mesh characteristics, surface structures, and realistic fluid parameters. [3]

In this work, a straight vessel with a diameter of 0.004 m and a height of 0.02 m is investigated. Thus, the flow domain $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is defined as $\Omega = \{\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid x \leq r \cdot \sin(\varphi), y \leq r \cdot \cos(\varphi), z = [-0.01, 0.01], r = 0.002, \varphi = [0, 2\pi]\}$ with physical borders as rigid walls. The inlet and outlet boundaries are the circular end faces of the vessel. The fluid dynamics are modeled using the Navier Stokes Equations (NSE) for incompressible, Newtonian fluids. To obtain the data, the *Finite volume solver STAR-CCM+ 14.04* is used. Moreover, the simulation setup is given as:

- tetrahedral mesh with base size 0.1 mm
- const. density $\rho = 1055 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$
- const. dynamic viscosity $\eta = 0.004 \text{ Pa s}$
- const. turbulence intensity 0.01
- const. turbulence viscosity ratio 10

Section 3.1 will provide a basic derivation of the Navier stokes equations in the following. Section 3.2 then proposes a modeling approach for applying the DMDc algorithm on NSE-based simulation data assuming the mass inflow as the control input.

3.1. Navier Stokes equations

This section gives a brief derivation of the Navier Stokes equations for an incompressible, Newtonian fluid. It is mainly based on [13], [15] and [32].

Leaving out the details of the Reynolds transport theorem, we consider the law of conservation of mass in its differential form as given:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \bullet (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (3.1.1)$$

Since we assume blood to be incompressible, hence $\rho = \text{const}$, we get that

$$\nabla \bullet \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (3.1.2)$$

Now, for the derivation of the motion of a viscous fluid, we start with Newton's second law of motion.

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{d(m \mathbf{v})}{dt} \quad (3.1.3)$$

With the aim of a volume-specific force on a time independent volume we can make the following transformations:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{d(\rho V \mathbf{v})}{dt} \quad (3.1.4)$$

$$d\mathbf{F} = \frac{d(\rho \mathbf{v})}{dt} dV \leftrightarrow \frac{d\mathbf{F}}{dV} = \frac{d(\rho \mathbf{v})}{dt} \quad (3.1.5)$$

Furthermore, we obtain the total derivative of the momentum $\rho \mathbf{v}$ remembering the incompressible characteristic of the fluid and making use of the chain rule

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(\rho \mathbf{v})}{dt} &= \rho \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} + \mathbf{v} \frac{d\rho}{dt} \\ &\stackrel{(3.1.2)}{=} \rho \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} \\ &= \rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \bullet \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.6)$$

which includes the material derivative of the velocity \mathbf{v} .

The forces acting on the volume can then be modeled as a sum of three parts:

- pressure forces F_p
- inner forces F_i given as fluid stresses due to viscosity
- external forces F_g given as the gravity force on the volume

The pressure force can be written in integral form:

$$\mathbf{F}_p = - \oint p \cdot \mathbf{n} dA \quad (3.1.7)$$

Using the divergence theorem, we get the volume-specific pressure force:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{F}}{dV} = -\nabla p \quad (3.1.8)$$

In terms of the inner forces, we consider the definition

$$\mathbf{F}_i = \oint \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} dA = \int \nabla \bullet \boldsymbol{\sigma} dV \quad (3.1.9)$$

including the well known viscous stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ given as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = 2\eta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} + \left(\zeta - \frac{2}{3}\eta\right) \mathbf{I} \nabla \bullet \mathbf{v} \quad (3.1.10)$$

with the *dynamic viscosity* η , the *volume viscosity* or *second viscosity* ζ , and the *strain rate tensor* $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$.

$$\epsilon_{i,j} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (3.1.11)$$

Note that in this case, the expression (3.1.10) becomes simpler since the last term is zero for incompressible fluids. Furthermore, again using (3.1.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \bullet \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i,*} &= \eta \sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \\ &= \eta \left(\sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial x_j^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_j} \right) \\ &= \eta \sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial x_j^2} \\ &= \eta \Delta v_i \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.12)$$

Finally, using Newton's second law of motion again with $\mathbf{F}_g = m\mathbf{g}$, we can express the volume-specific gravity force as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{F}_g}{dV} = \rho \mathbf{g} \quad (3.1.13)$$

Combining now the equations (3.1.5) and (3.1.6) with the derived forces in (3.1.8), (3.1.12), and (3.1.13), we obtain the Navier Stokes equations for an incompressible, Newtonian fluid:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \bullet \nabla) \mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p = \nu \Delta \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{g} \quad (3.1.14)$$

with the *kinematic viscosity* $\nu = \eta / \rho$.

This equation can furthermore be transformed in a more general form like

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} - \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{v}) = R \quad (3.1.15)$$

representing linear and nonlinear terms with respect to \mathbf{v} as well as a right side. Using a differential quotient for the time derivative we further get

$$\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \mathbf{v}_k + \Delta t \left(\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}_k - \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{v}_k) + R \right) \quad (3.1.16)$$

In the context of spatial discretization with the Finite Volume Method and the ensuing application of DMD, this term then represents the familiar expression known from (2.1.5) or (2.1.10), respectively.

3.2. Parametric modeling

In CFD, an appropriate selection of parameters in any aspect is crucial. Therefore it is necessary to evaluate and constantly improve the simulation and flow results for different influences or system variables. In terms of hemodynamic modeling and its clinical application, it is thus of high interest to obtain patient-specific CFD models quickly. [2]

Even though algorithms and computers become continuously more powerful and so computing time decreases, running a full CFD simulation is still time-consuming, which is, however, a standard procedure. This is economically inefficient, as calculating times can rise to several days on powerful computing servers. [14] Moreover, this practice also remains yet not applicable in the context of real-time systems or clinical context. [6] To that effect, a ROM to quickly evaluate different parametric scenarios with no need for huge hardware architectures appears promising. [6, 14]

In the following, we want to examine the effect of the inflow rhythm as a system variable for later use in DMDc. This inflow \mathbf{v}_{inlet} is usually characterized by a parabolic pattern in a geometrical sense to preserve the common boundary condition $\mathbf{v}|_{\partial\Omega} = 0$. Therefore, the following expression is suggested

$$\mathbf{v}_{inlet} = \tilde{\mathbf{v}} = \alpha \cdot \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (3.2.1)$$

where $\mathbf{P} : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the parabolic inflow pattern as a function of space. Although it is defined over the complete flow domain Ω , it only contains nonzero elements in the inlet area. Furthermore, to take the mass flow rate \dot{m} into account, we suppose that $\alpha = \dot{m}\beta$ with a constant coefficient β . In terms of consistency, we also have to consider the units of those values. We state that the inflow pattern has $[\mathbf{P}] = 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Since $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ itself has this unit, α has to have no unit. Given the fact that $[\dot{m}] = 1 \text{ kg s}^{-1}$ we get that $[\beta] = 1 \text{ s kg}^{-1}$. In this simplified consideration, β is only necessary for the consistency of units.

Complex blood flow simulations run unsteady since cardiac cycles are presented. Thus, we want to examine the effect of a time-dependent mass-flow rate at the inlet of the domain, hence $\alpha = \alpha(t)$. To include this dynamic inflow pattern in the NSE, we propose the following approach: The aim is to have $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$, which is a boundary condition, as a system parameter. Therefore we state the global velocity variable \mathbf{v}_g as a superposition of $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ and the actual system variable of the velocity $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$.

$$\mathbf{v}_g = \tilde{\mathbf{v}} + \hat{\mathbf{v}} \quad (3.2.2)$$

Applying this to (3.1.14) delivers for each term separately:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_g}{\partial t} &= \dot{\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{v}}}{\partial t} \\ &= \partial_t \dot{m} \cdot \beta \cdot \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{v}}}{\partial t} \\ &= \partial_t \dot{m} \cdot \mathbf{f}_1(\mathbf{P}, \beta) + \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{v}}}{\partial t} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{v}_g \bullet \nabla) \mathbf{v}_g &= \alpha^2 \cdot (\mathbf{P} \bullet \nabla) \mathbf{P} + \alpha \left[(\hat{\mathbf{v}} \bullet \nabla) \mathbf{P} + (\mathbf{P} \bullet \nabla) \hat{\mathbf{v}} \right] + (\hat{\mathbf{v}} \bullet \nabla) \hat{\mathbf{v}} \\ &= (\dot{m})^2 \cdot \mathbf{f}_2(\hat{\mathbf{v}}, \mathbf{P}, \beta^2) + \dot{m} \cdot \mathbf{f}_3(\hat{\mathbf{v}}, \mathbf{P}, \beta) + (\hat{\mathbf{v}} \bullet \nabla) \hat{\mathbf{v}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu \Delta \mathbf{v}_g &= \nu \alpha \cdot \Delta \mathbf{P} + \nu \Delta \hat{\mathbf{v}} \\ &= \nu \cdot \dot{m} \cdot \mathbf{f}_4(\mathbf{P}, \beta) + \nu \Delta \hat{\mathbf{v}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.5)$$

With these results, one can now reformulate and reshape (3.1.14) as

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{v}}}{\partial t} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_1 & \mathbf{f}_2 & \mathbf{f}_3 & \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + (\hat{\mathbf{v}} \bullet \nabla) \hat{\mathbf{v}} = \nu \Delta \hat{\mathbf{v}} + \mathbf{g} \quad (3.2.6)$$

with

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_t \dot{m} \\ (\dot{m})^2 \\ \dot{m} \\ \nu \cdot \dot{m} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.2.7)$$

Note that the functions $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_i$ are \mathbf{f}_i with changed signs, and \dot{m} is the mass-flow rate input given to the simulation program. We assume having separate data for the input mass-flow rate with a higher resolution in time than the CFD simulation. In doing so, let k be the index of the CFD time step and q the corresponding index in this input data set. Then we can approximate $\partial_t \dot{m}$ in \mathbf{u}_k with the differential quotient

$$\partial_t \dot{m} \approx \frac{\dot{m}_q - \dot{m}_{q-1}}{t_q - t_{q-1}} \quad (3.2.8)$$

Rearranging the equation in (3.2.6) using a differential quotient for the velocity delivers

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{k+1} &= \hat{\mathbf{v}}_k + \Delta t \left(\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_1 & \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_2 & \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_3 & \mathbf{f}_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{1,k} \\ y_{2,k} \\ y_{3,k} \\ y_{4,k} \end{bmatrix} - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p - (\hat{\mathbf{v}}_k \bullet \nabla) \hat{\mathbf{v}}_k + \nu \Delta \hat{\mathbf{v}}_k + \mathbf{g} \right) \\ &= \hat{\mathbf{v}}_k + \Delta t \left(-\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p - (\hat{\mathbf{v}}_k \bullet \nabla) \hat{\mathbf{v}}_k + \nu \Delta \hat{\mathbf{v}}_k + \mathbf{g} \right) + \Delta t \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_1 & \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_2 & \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_3 & \mathbf{f}_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{1,k} \\ y_{2,k} \\ y_{3,k} \\ y_{4,k} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.9)$$

Since the expression in the first brackets is already known from (3.1.16), this can be further simplified as

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{M} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_k + \Delta t \cdot \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{u}_k \quad (3.2.10)$$

which finally exhibits great similarity with (2.2.1) known from DMDc.

4. Experiment description

4.1. Configuration and criteria

The used snapshot data set consists of a five-cycle interval with a constant step size of $h = 0.02\text{ s}$, i.e., a total number of 250 snapshots. One cycle is of length 1 s. Here, n is 5136636, although Ω is relatively simple with a rather coarse base mesh size. Let \mathbf{X}_k denote the states of dimension n . Each snapshot is defined as $\mathbf{X}_k = [\mathbf{v}_x; \mathbf{v}_y; \mathbf{v}_z]$, i.e. only the velocity data is investigated. Thereby, their three dimensions are stacked.

To evaluate the presented algorithmic approaches, the calculations are carried out using the original DMD algorithm presented in section 2.1. Three methods were discussed to compute the reconstructed time steps $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_k$:

- The discrete ROM in (2.1.21).
- The discrete modal projection in (2.1.7).
- The time-domain version in (2.1.2).

It is to be noted that both discrete variants can only reconstruct states with the same step size as given in \mathbb{X} or \mathbb{X}' , respectively.

In terms of evaluation, different aspects are investigated, each for different setups: The most fundamental ability of DMD is to reconstruct the given snapshots. So first, the discrepancy between the simulation and the reconstructed data will be investigated. Secondly, extrapolation in time is a promising application. Therefore, we examine the question: Is the model capable of predicting states in time of which no data was supplied? In addition, the results will be investigated according to their setups.

Both DMD and DMDc are evaluated for *full size*, i.e., non-truncated models. However, since the number of necessary snapshots might rapidly grow for complex systems, further reduction is an essential part of MOR. That's why the results for truncated models are discussed in more detail. Here, truncation refers to the SVD steps in sections 2.1 and 2.2. For DMD, the examination is carried out using the time domain version. The DMDc calculations apply the parametric modeling presented in section 3.2. For this purpose, the inflow pattern in image 4.1a is used.

To investigate the capability of DMDC describing the system's behavior with other setups, the alternative inflow in image 4.1b is utilized.

Additionally, the stability of the reduced-order models will be evaluated.

Figure 4.1.: Mass inflow rates \dot{m} - Left image (a) shows the mass inflow rate \dot{m} used for most calculations. Right image (b) pictures the alternative input \dot{m} for the parametric projection

4.2. Evaluation variables

To investigate the simulation results, the relative error of the reconstructed state $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ is calculated at every time step k , i.e.

$$\varepsilon_k = \frac{\left| \mathbf{X}_k - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_k \right|}{\left| \mathbf{X}_k \right|} \quad (4.2.1)$$

The index k does not necessarily correspond to the ones in \mathbb{X} since the time domain solution may also be evaluated at different points in time.

Examining and comparing the results, different variables are used.

First, there are variables to measure the method's complexity. Those refer to the cost of the needed snapshots, e.g., from FVM simulation, and to the memory necessary to store the ROM results, like \mathbf{V} , $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ or \mathbf{U} . They are given by the *ROM dimension* r , the number of used *cycles* ζ of the periodic snapshots as well as the used *step size* h . Thus, r and $csteps = \zeta/h$ are supposed to be small. Moreover, they will be used as indicators for the simulation setup.

Secondly, variables to evaluate how well the model represents the original system

are considered. The *sample standard deviation* s describes the fluctuation of the relative error along the snapshots being assessed. Furthermore, the *maximal relative error* ξ alongside the given interval and the *average rel. error* along the interval $\bar{\epsilon} = (\sum_k \epsilon_k)/csteps$ are investigated. Consequently, s , ξ , and $\bar{\epsilon}$ are supposed to be small. Depending on the examined algorithmic version, $\bar{\epsilon}$ can have different references. For example, $\bar{\epsilon}_{rec}$ refers to the discrete reconstructed states along ζ . The mean relative error of the states computed with the time domain solution at additional points in time is given by $\bar{\epsilon}_{t,rec}$. Then there is $\bar{\epsilon}_{proj}$ which relates to the projected states at $t > \zeta$.

Additionally, EW_{unst} denotes the number of unstable eigenvalues of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$. The corresponding criteria will be explained in the following section.

4.3. Stability criteria

In studying dynamic systems, one of the most important features to investigate is stability. Looking at equation (2.1.2), a general criteria can be derived:

A linear dynamical system without perturbation ($\mathbf{u}(t) = 0$) is stable in the sense of Lyapunov [16] if

$$Re(\mu_i) \leq 0 \quad \forall \mu_i \text{ in } \Lambda \quad (4.3.1)$$

The eigenvalues with vanishing real parts must be semisimple, i.e., the algebraic multiplicity equals the geometric multiplicity. Otherwise, the matrix exponential combined with the arising Jordan blocks would produce unboundedly growing terms in time. [4]

Furthermore, if all the eigenvalues satisfy

$$Re(\mu_i) < 0 \quad \forall \mu_i \text{ in } \Lambda \quad (4.3.2)$$

the system is called asymptotically stable. [16] This is equivalent to *BIBO* stability, i.e., the system's output is bounded for every bounded input $\mathbf{u}(t)$. In the application of this work, the second definition is much more important. On the one hand, DMDc models a system with non-vanishing perturbation. On the other hand, even though DMD does not have a term \mathbf{u} in its ROM expression, we know that the original system is affected by an input.

Adapting these criteria to the discretized ROM in (2.1.21) leads to the following conditions:

Let $\mu = a + ib$ be a complex eigenvalue of \mathfrak{A} satisfying (4.3.1). Evaluating the eigenvalues λ_i of \mathbf{A} with (2.1.6) states that

$$|\lambda_i| = |e^{\mu_i \cdot h}| = |e^{a \cdot h}| \cdot |e^{ib \cdot h}| = |e^{a \cdot h}| \cdot 1 \leq 1 \quad (4.3.3)$$

Thus, the ROMs in (2.1.7) and (2.2.2) are Lyapunov stable if

$$|\lambda_i| \leq 1 \quad \forall \lambda_i \text{ in } \mathbf{A} \quad (4.3.4)$$

or asymptotically stable if

$$|\lambda_i| < 1 \quad \forall \lambda_i \text{ in } \mathbf{A} \quad (4.3.5)$$

In a more general form for time-discrete linear systems, these results for Lyapunov and *BIBO* stability can equivalently be found in [17].

In addition, the more the eigenvalues violate (4.3.4), the more unstable the corresponding modes are. The higher the number of unstable eigenvalues, the more modes grow unboundedly. Hence, their total number and the deviation are supposed to vanish, or at least to be small.

5. Results and evaluation

5.1. Representation in a low dimensional model

5.1.1. Full-size DMD

Using DMD without further truncation produces highly accurate results when reconstructing the snapshots, see the results in table 5.1. Keeping the original step size h on reconstruction, the average relative error among all test setups on the original interval ζ is 2×10^{-8} . This result is, however, not surprising. Here, the algorithm transforms the snapshots into an equivalent mapping. Since no approximations, i.e., truncations, are made, the only remaining errors are the propagated numerical and approximation errors.

When h is made smaller using the time domain solution, the discrepancy between the solution and FVM data enlarges. It can be thought of as the ROM interpolating the snapshots, fig. 5.1. The range of the relative errors $\bar{\epsilon}_{t,rec}$ of the interpolated points are 0.3% to 2%, which is an appropriate magnitude for application.

Regarding the projection, the relative error increases. Still, choosing an adequate setup and keeping the original input step size, an average relative error of $\bar{\epsilon}_{proj} = 2\%$ can be achieved. The maximum ξ , however, can reach 20 to 30%, whereas the standard deviation s goes from 3 to 8%.

If choosing a different, e.g., smaller h , the relative error in projection exhibits great similarity with those of the original step size, as seen in figures 5.1 and C.1. So, the step size used in reconstruction is not of great importance for projection and can thus be chosen differently without an accuracy fall-off.

Observing the chosen setups in table 5.1 shows that the result's quality is proportional to ζ , i.e., the number of utilized cycles. Also, a tendency towards a larger number of snapshots r can be observed. This mentioned correlation becomes more apparent when looking at the singular value plot in figure 5.2a. Although the singular values drop rapidly and form a plateau for r above 30, they are not easily negligible from thereon. In terms of singular values, the magnitude is still relatively high with 10^{-2} , and so, the error increases noticeably the fewer snapshots are used.

h in s	ζ	r	s	ξ	$\bar{\epsilon}_{rec}$	$\bar{\epsilon}_{t,rec}$	$\bar{\epsilon}_{proj}$	EW_{unst}
0.04	3.0	74	0.029	0.111	3.711×10^{-8}	0.005	0.018	0
0.06	3.0	49	0.038	0.188	2.812×10^{-8}	0.019	0.025	0
0.04	1.5	36	0.058	0.301	4.522×10^{-8}	0.005	0.040	0
0.02	1.5	74	0.047	0.193	3.868×10^{-8}	—	0.046	0
0.06	1.5	24	0.081	0.390	1.395×10^{-8}	0.020	0.084	0
0.02	1.0	49	0.091	0.366	1.184×10^{-8}	—	0.134	0
0.04	1.0	24	0.154	0.631	4.371×10^{-9}	0.003	0.251	2
0.06	1.0	15	4.040	19.173	1.128×10^{-9}	0.007	3.811	2

Table 5.1.: Calculation results - full-size DMD

Figure 5.1.: Full-size DMD interpolation for $h = 0.04, r = 74, \zeta = 3.0$ - The green shows the time solution with initial snapshot step size. Orange pictures the solution for arbitrary h , here $h = 0.02$

5.1.2. Truncated DMD

The most significant difference to the full-size model is that the truncated model exhibits no explicit reconstruction interval with vanishing errors on ζ . Thus, no concrete differentiation between reconstruction and projection exists. However, an average relative deviation of 2% and a maximum deviation ξ of around 10% can be obtained by those ROMs. Also, the standard deviation proves the good results of the truncated DMD with $s = 1 - 4\%$.

By using the time-domain version to calculate solutions at arbitrary points in time, the calculations show similar characteristics as the full-size models. As pictured in figures 5.3,C.2 and table 5.2, the deviation differs very little.

Figure 5.2.: Singular values for different sets - Left image (a) shows the plotted singular values for different full-size DMD models. The right image (b) pictures the equivalent results various truncated models.

Evaluating the considered setups, it again seems to reveal a connection between truncation rank and accuracy. This can equivalently be rooted in the singular value properties of this model as described in section 5.1.1, see figure 5.2b.

Figure 5.3.: Truncated DMD interpolation for $h = 0.04, r = 50, \zeta = 3.0$ - The green shows the time solution with initial snapshot step size. Orange pictures the solution for arbitrary h , here $h = 0.02$

h in s	ζ	r	s	ξ	$\bar{\epsilon}$	$\bar{\epsilon}_t$	EW_{unst}
0.04	4.2	50	0.007	0.041	0.009	0.010	3
0.04	4.2	35	0.009	0.055	0.010	0.011	3
0.04	3.0	50	0.023	0.107	0.019	0.020	0
0.04	3.0	35	0.024	0.113	0.021	0.021	0
0.06	4.2	50	0.023	0.170	0.019	0.022	0
0.04	1.5	35	0.038	0.211	0.024	0.024	0
0.02	1.5	50	0.045	0.237	0.040	0.040	1
0.04	1.5	23	0.082	0.374	0.071	0.071	0
0.02	3.0	50	0.066	0.345	0.053	0.053	0
0.02	4.2	50	0.063	0.366	0.050	0.050	0
0.06	1.5	23	0.096	0.441	0.091	0.090	0
0.04	3.0	23	0.086	0.370	0.082	0.082	0
0.06	4.2	35	0.087	0.431	0.073	0.074	0
0.06	1.5	15	0.103	0.434	0.110	0.110	0
0.06	3.0	35	0.097	0.419	0.090	0.090	0
0.04	1.5	15	0.101	0.423	0.107	0.107	0
0.04	4.2	23	0.091	0.396	0.085	0.086	1
0.02	1.5	35	0.094	0.414	0.096	0.096	0
0.04	3.0	15	0.100	0.415	0.105	0.105	0
0.06	4.2	23	0.101	0.434	0.099	0.099	0
0.06	3.0	23	0.103	0.463	0.103	0.103	0
0.04	4.2	15	0.100	0.414	0.105	0.105	1
0.06	3.0	15	0.102	0.463	0.119	0.119	0
0.06	4.2	15	0.101	0.450	0.119	0.118	0
0.02	1.5	23	0.102	0.463	0.114	0.114	0
0.02	1.5	15	0.106	0.461	0.121	0.121	0
0.02	3.0	15	0.097	0.432	0.115	0.115	0
0.02	3.0	23	0.095	0.451	0.114	0.114	0
0.02	4.2	15	0.098	0.433	0.117	0.117	0
0.02	3.0	35	0.104	0.498	0.114	0.114	0
0.02	4.2	23	0.100	0.483	0.118	0.118	0
0.02	4.2	35	0.105	0.516	0.116	0.116	0

Table 5.2.: Calculation results - truncated DMD

5.1.3. Full-size DMDc

As expected, the DMDc algorithm also provides accurate reconstruction when the model is not truncated. Here, the mean relative error among all setups is 5×10^{-11} and thus even lower than for the standard algorithm, see table 5.3.

Comparing table 5.3 with table 5.1 in terms of projection, it can be seen that both algorithms deliver similar results for equal setups. So the error magnitude of DMD can likewise be achieved with DMDc using full-size models. Also, ξ with 4 – 30% and $s = 1 - 8\%$ match the full-size DMD version.

Examining the effect of the model setup appears to be less distinct with DMDc. Still, using multiple cycles ζ with a higher step size h will likely produce better results. That seems reasonable since the dynamics depend on the periodic input, which can only be represented if multiple cycles are covered.

h in s	ζ	r	s	ξ	$\bar{\epsilon}_{rec}$	$\bar{\epsilon}_{proj}$	EW_{unst}
0.06	4.2	69	0.007	0.022	4.254×10^{-11}	0.012	19
0.04	2.2	54	0.010	0.040	6.190×10^{-11}	0.010	13
0.04	1.5	36	0.053	0.280	2.793×10^{-11}	0.048	2
0.06	2.2	35	0.060	0.252	3.018×10^{-11}	0.061	4
0.06	1.5	24	0.084	0.349	1.927×10^{-11}	0.091	0
0.02	1.0	49	0.111	0.451	5.299×10^{-11}	0.170	0
0.02	2.2	109	0.152	0.625	1.153×10^{-10}	0.119	21
0.02	1.5	74	0.967	5.056	6.241×10^{-11}	0.692	8
0.06	1.0	15	4.199	19.974	1.363×10^{-11}	2.824	2

Table 5.3.: Calculation results - full-size DMDc

5.1.4. Truncated DMDc

As with DMD, truncating a DMDc model prohibits an accurate reconstruction. But in contrast to DMD, truncating the model leads to more gross deviations. See the results in table 5.4. The best average relative errors among the tested setups are around 12 %. Furthermore, the mean maximum ξ is 45 %, and the standard deviation has a magnitude of 10 %. Thus, truncated DMDc is little applicable for reconstruction or projection.

Contrary to the previous evaluations, the truncated DMDc generates comparatively better results with lower dimensions.

h in s	ζ	r	s	ξ	$\bar{\epsilon}$	EW_{unst}
0.06	1.5	15	0.103	0.453	0.120	0
0.02	1.0	15	0.097	0.458	0.111	0
0.06	2.2	15	0.099	0.466	0.128	0
0.02	1.5	15	0.102	0.457	0.117	0
0.06	3.0	15	0.101	0.487	0.141	0
0.06	3.0	35	0.121	0.420	0.152	2
0.02	1.0	35	0.124	0.475	0.165	0
0.06	3.1	50	0.587	2.805	0.316	22
0.02	1.1	50	1.043	5.136	0.662	7
0.02	1.5	35	2.207	11.202	1.542	2

Table 5.4.: Calculation results - truncated DMDc

5.2. Parametric projection with DMDc

5.2.1. Full-size DMDc

The first interesting fact to notice is that there seems to be no strict relation between producing accurate results in the original and parametric projection. This becomes clear when comparing $\bar{\epsilon}$ in table 5.5 with the order of $\bar{\epsilon}_{proj}$ in table 5.3.

Secondly, non of the tested setups could produce ROMs to reasonably describe the behavior with the alternative parametric input. Non achieved an $\bar{\epsilon}$ under 140%. Equivalently, the maximal errors are not smaller than 800%, and the relative deviations are more extensive than 130% towards the mean.

h in s	ζ	r	s	ξ	$\bar{\epsilon}$	EW_{unst}
0.06	4.2	69	4.515	21.864	5.248	19
0.04	2.2	54	4.135	16.694	5.801	13
0.04	1.5	36	2.807	14.822	2.987	2
0.06	2.2	35	3.985	20.511	4.879	4
0.06	1.5	24	1.316	8.728	1.389	0
0.02	1.0	49	2.228	14.779	1.514	0
0.02	2.2	109	1799.838	9968.964	879.465	21
0.02	1.5	74	826.131	4653.082	442.406	8
0.06	1.0	15	32.740	115.427	22.077	2

Table 5.5.: Parametric projection results - full-size DMDc

5.2.2. Truncated DMDc

As opposed to the full-size variant, for the truncated DMDc the quality relation concerning the setup seems to hold equally with the original and parametric projection. Moreover, the truncated version generally produces better results for the alternative parameter than the previous version. It is even possible to obtain a description with a mean relative deviation under 100%, which, however, appears unlikely. Although better than in the full-size variant, ξ is still above 400%, and the model's errors exhibit a scatter s of around 80% at best, see table 5.6.

h in s	ζ	r	s	ξ	$\bar{\epsilon}$	EW_{unst}
0.06	1.5	15	0.707	4.383	1.092	0
0.02	1.0	15	1.054	8.835	0.848	0
0.06	2.2	15	0.811	5.555	1.116	0
0.02	1.5	15	1.858	13.734	1.199	0
0.06	3.0	15	0.812	4.382	1.130	0
0.06	3.0	35	1.885	7.883	3.128	2
0.02	1.0	35	2.049	15.052	1.725	0
0.06	3.1	50	40.039	248.139	27.889	22
0.02	1.1	50	367.714	1675.668	231.502	7
0.02	1.5	35	203.093	908.691	145.182	2

Table 5.6.: Parametric projection results - truncated DMDc

5.3. Stability

5.3.1. Full-size DMD

As shown in table 5.1, the full-size DMD version generally produces BIBO stable ROMs. Only two tested setups satisfied neither equation (4.3.4) nor (4.3.5). However, those do also have higher deviations in general. Thus, the stability correlates with the overall quality of the results.

5.3.2. Truncated DMD

Generally, truncating a DMD model produces BIBO stable ROMs, see table 5.2. Few exceptions exist, mainly with the setup $h = 0.04$ and $\zeta = 4.2$. In every case, the set of unstable eigenvalues includes $\lambda = 1$ with a slight deviation at 10^{-7} . Nevertheless, if it's the only eigenvalue violating the stability condition, the corresponding model might still be considered Lyapunov stable.

Furthermore, other unstable eigenvalues might appear, e.g., with setups one and two in table 5.2. In both cases, the eigenvalues violate the condition (4.3.4) at 10^{-4} . Although this is not a vast transgression, the deviation and thus the effect is more significant than with 10^{-7} .

But due to their minor relative errors $\bar{\epsilon}$, they still produce an appropriate representation when applied on a short interval, see figure C.3.

5.3.3. Full-size DMDc

In contrast to DMD, the full-size DMDc delivers an unstable ROM with almost every chosen setup, table 5.3. The deviations go from 10^{-7} to 10^{-2} , which, combined with

the often large amount of unstable eigenvalues, produces noticeably fast-growing errors, as shown in figure C.4.

It appears that the number of unstable eigenvalues is proportional to the rank of the model. The effect of the unstable eigenvalues can impressively be seen in the parametric projection in table 5.5 when comparing the last two columns. Since not only the number but also the amplitude of the unstable eigenvalues matters, unstable models might still produce very good solutions on finite intervals, see figure C.5.

5.3.4. Truncated DMDc

It is more likely to obtain stable ROMs using the truncated DMDc version. Most of the setups are BIBO stable, as shown in table 5.4. Again, there seems to be a correlation with the rank r of the ROM. Moreover, the slightly truncated ones exhibit a significantly higher amount of unstable eigenvalues.

Again, the effect becomes distinct in the parametric projection, see table 5.6.

5.4. Model characteristics

5.4.1. DMD approaches

In section 2.1, three approaches were introduced to calculate solutions using the results of the DMD algorithm. The mathematical derivation justifies that all provide similar results. Up to which extent this is true in a numerical sense, is presented in figure 5.4. The absolute difference between the method's results was chosen for evaluation since it provides a better understanding than the relative.

The modal projection and the time-domain version are equal with an accuracy of 10^{-10} to 10^{-15} , i.e., almost machine precision. This result confirms the transformation in (2.1.22). The ROM version, however, exhibits a deviation of ca. 10^{-6} from the others remaining. This result was covered in transformation (2.1.23).

5.4.2. Parametric modeling

Section 3.2 engaged in reasonably modeling the DMDc algorithm and the NSE such that the mass inflow \dot{m} becomes the control input $\mathbf{u}(t)$ in (2.2.1). This paragraph is dedicated to briefly evaluate the success of the mentioned approach in terms of its ability to improve the application of DMDc and its parametric projection.

Therefore, the derived input vector in (3.2.7) is replaced by the scalar \dot{m} . Three different DMDc setups are compared to examine whether the modeled version provides better solutions or if it makes a difference at all. Figure C.6 shows that both approaches generally cover the system's behavior and exhibit similar

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.4.: Evaluation of DMD approaches - Each of the figures shows the solution errors ε for all three methods (yellow, blue, pink). The other lines represent the absolute deviations between the ε of two methods each. (green, black, red) Image (a) for set1 = $\{h = 0.02, \zeta = 2.2, r = 45\}$, set2 = $\{h = 0.06, \zeta = 3, r = 45\}$

characteristics. Thus, a more detailed comparison seems reasonable.

The presented results are obtained as follows. Let $\varepsilon_{mod,k}$ be the relative error vector of the modeled version at index k . Additionally, $\varepsilon_{simp,k}$ denotes the error vector of the simplified m variant. The difference between both is given as $\delta_k = \varepsilon_{mod,k} - \varepsilon_{simp,k}$. Consequently, if the modeled version has a more minor error, thus better result, δ_k is negative. Absolute deviations may differ significantly depending on the setup and

whether prediction or parametric projection is reviewed. Therefore, it is scaled with $\varepsilon_{simp,k}$ to obtain a relative impression Δ of their deviation between 0 and 1 - vice versa for the simplified version. Thus, if Δ is close to zero, both approaches are similar. The bigger Δ , the more accurate one of both is.

$$\Delta_k = \begin{cases} \frac{\delta_k}{\varepsilon_{mod,k}} & \text{if } \delta_k \geq 0 \\ \frac{\delta_k}{\varepsilon_{simp,k}} & \text{if } \delta_k < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5.4.1)$$

The results are shown in figure 5.5 and table 5.7. Regarding the DMDc prediction, the modeled version generally produces results with slightly smaller errors. This tendency seems to depend on the chosen set. Due to the small sample size, however, no statements about correlations can be made. Nevertheless, the difference between the two methods appears small according to the areas of small values in figure 5.5.

The difference of methods for the parametric projection vanishes in the mean. In general, the modeled and simplified versions are similar for projection, as 49 % of all values are in the range of ± 0.2 .

Figure 5.5.: Evaluation of modeling approach - set1 = $\{h = 0.02, \zeta = 1, r = 49\}$, set2 = $\{h = 0.04, \zeta = 2.2, r = 54\}$, set3 = $\{h = 0.06, \zeta = 2.2, r = 15\}$. Set1 and set2 are full-size models. Left image (a) shows the results of all sets for the standard DMDc reconstruction and prediction according to equation (5.4.1). Right image (b) pictures the equivalent results for the parametric projection.

	Std. prediction	param. projection
$\Delta < 0$	68 %	53 %
$\Delta_{set1} < 0$	76 %	63 %
$\Delta_{set2} < 0$	54 %	39 %
$\Delta_{set3} < 0$	66 %	46 %
$ \Delta < 0.1$	21 %	30 %
$ \Delta < 0.2$	39 %	49 %

Table 5.7.: Evaluation of parametric modeling approach

5.4.3. Transient process

The models obtained by the different DMD methods represent dynamic systems. Those systems are likely to show a transient process when the input changes. The transient process represents the system’s reaction to a sudden change of the previous state. It takes as long as the system to adapt to the change or until it reaches its steady state, respectively. This adaptation is not abrupt and needs a transitional phase. [30] In the case of periodic stimulation, the system migrates into a forced steady-state oscillation. This variation, however, is not necessarily sudden in practice. Depending on the system’s characteristics, every amplitude variation in time quicker than the system’s setting time induces a transient process. [25]

This property is observed upon the calculation results. The outcome, however, is not distinct. Several setups show a clear adaptation phase followed by a periodic steady state, see C.7. In some cases, the duration of the transient process is equal to ζ , especially with this precise behavior. It can be considered a guideline, but it is no rule and can vary as figs. C.8 and C.9 show. Often, the reduced-order models show a transient behavior with an *approximated steady state*. It means that they either develop a repetitive pattern, which is not periodic, or the error’s amplitude reaches a stationary range. For example, see figs. C.10 and C.11. Finally, C.12 pictures that a distinguishable transient process does not even has to be present at all.

Code and data availability

The source code of the implementations used to compute the presented results and all figures are available from

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under the MIT license and are authored by Konrad Schindler.

6. Discussion and Outlook

This work aims to investigate the DMD methodology according to its characteristics and ability to improve CFD-based hemodynamic research. Apart from the derivation of the mathematical fundamentals, also FVM data reconstruction, future state prediction, state interpolation, and parametric projection for the mass inflow rate were covered. To that effect, the calculations disclosed relevant properties and capabilities.

The average error, the maximum, and the time-dependent mean spread of the model deviation indicate the quality of the obtained models. In this regard, the calculations show impressively the consistency among these evaluation variables. Namely, all three values are proportional, significantly simplifying the setup choice.

The evaluation of the classic DMD algorithm is distinct. Whether truncated or not, it produces BIBO stable or at least approximatively Lyapunov stable models. Moreover, the small mean prediction deviation of 2 % is equal in both cases and can thus enable a fundamental system evaluation based on a small number of snapshots. On the one hand, the further reduced model claims less memory and provides a higher quality description, namely a relative error spread smaller than 4 % and a maximum around 10 %. On the other hand, the full-size model can fully reproduce the primarily given snapshots. , the model will additionally be able to future-state predict and interpolate. Consequently, the choice between the full-size and truncated model highly depends on the specific requirements. According to the results and the possibilities, the scientist can choose between the ROM in (2.1.21) or the time-domain solution in (2.1.2). Apart from future-state prediction, the time-domain version also seems to interpolate the discrete solutions well. However, the necessary matrices \mathbf{V} or \mathbf{U} would need the same amount of memory. In comparison, the discrete modal projection in (2.1.7) has no advantages. The ratio of storage savings is given as $r/(m-1)$ since either \mathbf{V} or \mathbf{U} dominate the memory usage due to their size.

The results of the DMDc algorithm, however, could not keep up with the expectations. In projection and reconstruction, the full-size version can produce similar results as the DMD method. Nevertheless, the models are usually unstable, and it requires higher cost in terms of calculation, data, and memory. The truncated DMDc models are indeed BIBO stable, but their relative errors $\bar{\epsilon}$ are on average 0.1 bigger than with DMD. The most exciting and desirable application is a parametric projection, i.e., describing the system's behavior for different parametric inputs. With deviations of

commonly more than 100%, appropriate parametric investigation using an input-output model can not be achieved. As a result, with this particular simple model, the DMDc algorithm is not able to improve the research procedure for system parameter evaluation. Thus, it can not live up to the predictions in [21].

It has to be mentioned, however, that algorithmic questions concerning DMDc are yet to investigate. The primary DMD method does reconstruction and projection based on the snapshot \mathbf{x}_1 , which must be stored additionally. With DMDc, this procedure does not provide relevant results. Among briefly tested initiation approaches like different index-shifting techniques, the one in (6.0.1) provided the best results. Thus, this approach was applied in the calculations, but there is no indication that it is the best.

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_1 = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \cdot (\hat{\mathbf{U}}_x^* \cdot \mathbf{x}_2 - \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}_1) \quad (6.0.1)$$

To investigate the capabilities of the DMDc algorithm predicting the system's behavior at different mass inflow rates, a modeling approach based on the NSE was provided in chapter 3.2. The results in section 5.4.2 show that this modeling induces no significant improvement. Although there is an advantage in applying it on reconstruction and prediction, the results are not expedient without the possibility of transferring the obtained information onto another parameter. The results are, however, not extensively surprising. Chapter 2.1 explained that DMD's fundamental force is to extract the dominant underlying behavior inherent in the given data. In this regard, the modeling approach includes the same information as the simplified variant, which only uses \dot{m} .

During the research, transient behavior was observed in the obtained models. Far from being investigated in detail, this property is mentioned for the awareness of a future adopter. The adaptation phase might affect the model's reconstruction accuracy and specific cases of applications.

Aside from providing results for each method individually, the comparability among those can only be taken as a basis. This limitation is due to an inconsistent setup choice. For more precise results and the elaboration of distinct statements, identical setups should be chosen for all methods. Furthermore, apart from the truncated DMD variant, the sample sizes are undersized compared with the number of possible setups. More extensive sets would make it possible to provide more precise suggestions for an appropriate setup choice and could allow a statistical examination of its effect on the results. Finally, for an even broader context, different geometries should be assessed.

So far, only quantitative investigations have been made and no qualitative. Spatially examining the accuracy was out of the scope of this work and so the errors might be distributed unequally. Therefore, the presented results are not inerrable concerning the practice. Especially in hemodynamics, not every spatial area is equally important due to wall-stress and aneurysm treatment. Thus, the solution's quality might come out differently due to application-dependent attention.

In addition to the already explained limitations and proposals, future research is needed to characterize periodicity in time solutions and investigate the abilities of DMD and DMDC concerning slightly perturbed or non-periodic systems and inputs. Moreover, continuative studies should consider system properties like the Strouhal number when choosing step sizes for the snapshots. Finally, the condition number of the problem could be another good reference to evaluate setup choices and solution qualities.

As hemodynamic CFD investigation and patient-specific treatment gains increasing significance, it is vital to research model reduction approaches that avoid expensive FVM simulations and make use of the vast amount of available data. Dynamic mode decomposition is a modal decomposition method that has already been successfully applied in various fields of computational fluid dynamics and thus exhibits great potential also to improve hemodynamic research. Aside from deriving three algorithmic variants of DMD, an NSE-based modeling approach is introduced to examine blood flow models on behalf of mass inflow characteristics. It could be shown that apart from precise reconstruction, DMD models can predict and interpolate flow variables at an accuracy of 10^{-2} only using snapshot data. Whereas the parameter-based DMD method cannot provide relevant results, the presented calculations are far from having included all necessary knowledge in current DMD, MOR, and CFD research. Nevertheless, different model properties like a transient process or method-dependent accuracy were revealed, and the DMD results have proven the method's potential to extract the system's behavior from data. DMD holds an immense assortment for mathematicians to survey. Thus, it provides a broad basis for considerations and collaborations of engineers and mathematicians to carve out appropriate data for desired features.

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Declaration of Originality

I confirm that the submitted thesis is original work and was written by me without further assistance. Appropriate credit has been given where reference has been made to the work of others. The thesis was not examined before, nor has it been published. The submitted electronic version of the thesis matches the printed version.

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Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die von mir vorgelegte Bachelorarbeit

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Magdeburg, 14.01.22

Place, date

Signature

Appendices

A. List of variables

Symbole	Meaning	Dimension / Unit
\mathbf{x} or \mathbf{X}	State vector	\mathbb{R}^n
$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$	State vector	\mathbb{R}^r
$\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$	Reconstructed state vector	\mathbb{R}^n
\mathcal{A}	ODE matrix	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$
t	time	s
\mathcal{V}	Exact DMD modes or eigenvector matrix of \mathcal{A}	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{n \times r}$
ν	Exact DMD modes	\mathbb{C}^n
$\tilde{\mathcal{V}}$	Projected DMD modes	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times r}$
\mathfrak{A}	Eigenvalue matrix of \mathcal{A}	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$
\mathbf{d}	The coordinates of \mathbf{x}_1 in the eigenvector-space \mathcal{V}	\mathbb{C}^n or \mathbb{C}^r
h	Time step size of the used snapshots	\mathbb{R}
\mathbf{A} or $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$	ROM DMD-matrix	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$
Λ	Eigenvalue matrix of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ or \mathbf{A}	$\mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$
λ_i	Eigenvalue from Λ	\mathbb{C}
μ_i	Eigenvalue from \mathfrak{A}	\mathbb{C}
\mathbb{X}	Snapshot matrix with index 1 to $m - 1$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times m-1}$
\mathbb{X}'	Shifted snapshot matrix with index 2 to m	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times m-1}$
\mathbf{U} or $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$	Left singular matrix of \mathbb{X}	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{n \times r}$
Σ or $\hat{\Sigma}$	Singular value matrix of \mathbb{X}	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times m-1}$ or $\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
\mathbf{V} or $\hat{\mathbf{V}}$	Right singular matrix of \mathbb{X}	$\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times m-1}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times r}$
\mathbf{W}	Eigenvector matrix of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$	$\mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$
\mathbf{B} or $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$	DMDc input matrix	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times p}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{r \times p}$
\mathcal{Y}	Input snapshot matrix with index 1 to $m - 1$	$\mathbb{R}^{p \times m-1}$
\mathbf{G}	Combined DMDc matrix = $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times n+p}$
\mathcal{K}	Combined DMDc snapshot matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n+p \times m-1}$
\mathbf{U}_o or $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_o$	Left singular matrix of \mathcal{K}	$\mathbb{C}^{n+p \times n+p}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{n+p \times s}$
Σ_o or $\hat{\Sigma}_o$	Singular value matrix of \mathcal{K}	$\mathbb{R}^{n+p \times m-1}$ or $\mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$
\mathbf{V}_o or $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_o$	Right singular matrix of \mathcal{K}	$\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times m-1}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times s}$
\mathbf{U}_x or $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_x$	Left singular matrix of \mathbb{X}'	$\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{n \times s}$

Σ_x or $\hat{\Sigma}_x$	Singular value matrix of \mathbb{X}'	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ or $\mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$
\mathbf{V}_x or $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_x$	Right singular matrix of \mathbb{X}'	$\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times m-1}$ or $\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times s}$
ϕ	Scaled, exact DMD modes	\mathbb{C}^n
Θ	$= \Sigma * \Sigma$, Eigenvalue matrix of \mathbf{H}	$\mathbb{R}^{m-1 \times m-1}$
\mathbf{H}	Correlation matrix of \mathbb{X}	$\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times m-1}$
\mathbf{H}'	$= \mathbf{H}_{1:m-1, 2:m-1}$	$\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times m-2}$
\mathbf{H}''	$(\mathbf{H}'')_i = \langle x_m, x_i \rangle$ for $i = 1 \dots m-1$	\mathbb{C}^{m-1}
\mathbf{T}	$= \mathbf{V}\Theta^{-\frac{1}{2}}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{D}$ matrix for efficient calculation	$\mathbb{C}^{m-1 \times r}$
\mathbf{D}	$diag(\mathbf{d})$	$\mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$
Ω	Flow domain	
ρ	Density	kg m^{-3}
η	Dynamic viscosity	Pa s
\mathbf{v}	Velocity	m s^{-1}
∇	Nabla operator	
σ	Viscous stress tensor	\mathbb{R}^3
\mathbf{g}	Gravitational acceleration	m s^{-2} , \mathbb{R}^3
α	Pre-factor of \mathbf{P}	\mathbb{R}
\mathbf{P}	Flow domain inflow pattern	\mathbb{R}^3
\dot{m}	Mass inflow rate	kg s^{-1} , \mathbb{R}
β	Factor in α necessary for unit consistency	s kg^{-1} , \mathbb{R}
$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$	Inflow velocity	m s^{-1} , \mathbb{R}^3
ν	Kinematic viscosity	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, \mathbb{R}
ε_k	Relative error of reconstructed state at index k	
ζ	Number of cycles used for snapshots	
r	Truncation rank	
s	Sample standard deviation	
ξ	Maximal relative error	
$\bar{\varepsilon}$	Mean relative error	
$\bar{\varepsilon}_{proj}$	Mean relative error of the projected interval	
$\bar{\varepsilon}_{t,rec}$	Mean relative error of the interpolated points in time on ζ	
$\bar{\varepsilon}_{rec}$	Mean relative error of the reconstructed states on ζ	
EW_{unst}	Number of unstable eigenvalues	
δ_k	Absolut error of ε_k for two different modeling approaches	
Δ_k	Relative error of ε_k based on δ_k	

B. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
BIBO	Bounded input bounded output
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
DDMOR	Data-driven model order reduction
DMD	Dynamic mode decomposition
DMDc	Dynamic mode decomposition with control
ERA	Eigensystem realization algorithm
FVM	Finite volume method
MOR	Model order reduction
NSE	Navier Stokes equations
ODE	Ordinary differential equation
OKID	Observer Kalman filter identification
PDE	Partial differential equation
POD	Proper orthogonal decomposition
ROM	Reduced-order model
SVD	Singular value decomposition

C. Images

Figure C.1.: Full-size DMD interpolation for $h = 0.04, r = 24, \zeta = 1.0$ - The green shows the time solution with initial snapshot step size. Orange pictures the solution for arbitrary h , here $h = 0.02$

Figure C.2.: Truncated DMD interpolation for $h = 0.06, r = 15, \zeta = 3.0$ - The green shows the time solution with initial snapshot step size. Orange pictures the solution for arbitrary h , here $h = 0.02$

Figure C.3.: Unstable truncated DMD with small errors for $h = 0.04, r = 50, \zeta = 4.2$ - Although the model has 3 unstable eigenvalues, it provides a description with small deviation on a finite interval

Figure C.4.: Unstable full-size DMDc parameter projection for $h = 0.02, r = 74, \zeta = 1.5$ - Having multiple eigenvalues that strongly violate the stability condition in (4.3.4), the relative errors of the model grow rapidly.

Figure C.5.: Unstable full-size DMDc with small errors for $h = 0.04, r = 54, \zeta = 2.2$ - Although the model has 13 unstable eigenvalues, it provides a description with small deviation on a finite interval

(a)

(b)

Figure C.6.: Evaluation of modeling approach - set1 = $\{h = 0.02, \zeta = 1, r = 49\}$, set2 = $\{h = 0.04, \zeta = 2.2, r = 54\}$, set3 = $\{h = 0.06, \zeta = 2.2, r = 15\}$. The figure shows relative errors comparing the simplified version with the modeling proposition. Different sets in different colors. Image (a) pictures DMDc projection results. Image (b) shows parametric DMDc projections.

Figure C.7.: Distinct transient process for truncated DMDc parameter projection with $h = 0.02, r = 15, \zeta = 1.5$ - This parametric projection shows a clear periodic steady state after an adaptation phase of precisely $1.5 \text{ s} = \zeta$

Figure C.8.: Distinct transient process for truncated DMD model with $h = 0.02, r = 15, \zeta = 4.2$ - This parametric projection shows a clear periodic steady state after an adaptation phase of $\approx 1.7 \text{ s}$, different to ζ

Figure C.9.: Approximate transient process for truncated DMDc parameter projection with $h = 0.02$, $r = 49$, $\zeta = 1.0$ - This parametric projection shows a transient process with an adaptation phase of ≈ 3.3 s, that is different to ζ , during which the rel. error drops. The steady state appears as an approximate periodic oscillation.

Figure C.10.: Approximate transient process for truncated DMD model with $h = 0.06$, $r = 23$, $\zeta = 3.0$ - The projection shows a transient process with an adaptation phase of ≈ 2.7 s, during which the rel. error grows. The steady state appears as an approximate periodic oscillation.

Figure C.11.: Approximate transient process for truncated DMD model with $h = 0.04, r = 23, \zeta = 1.5$ - The projection shows a transient process with an adaptation phase of $\approx 1.5 \text{ s} = \zeta$, during which the rel. error grows. The steady state appears as an approximate periodic oscillation.

Figure C.12.: Unclear transient process of truncated DMDc parameter projection with $h = 0.04, r = 54, \zeta = 2.2$ - This example demonstrates that a model might show no distinguishable transient process at all.